

Flavonoid glycosides of *Athyrium solenopteris* (Kunze) T. Moore of Palni Hills of South India

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Athyrium solenopteris (Kunze) T. Moore, an Athyroid fern is growing on fully shaded stream, banks, forest floor and fully exposed marshy place. It is commonly available in Nilgiris and Palni hills at an altitude of 2000–3000 m¹. Matured aerial parts of *A. solenopteris* (St. Xavier's College Herbarium Voucher No. RHT 32829) were collected from the Berijam lake of Palni hills of South India at an altitude of 2200 m. Five flavonoid glycosides, kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside, kaempferol-3-*O*-diglucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-diglucoside and quercetin-3-*O*-diglucoside-3'-*O*-xyloside have been isolated and characterised.

Results and discussion

On the basis of 2d PC, R_f values, UV-vis spectral data with shift reagent studies, acid hydrolysis, TLC studies of aglycones with authentic samples and by GLC studies (Table 1) the isolated compounds were identified as the following five flavonoid glycosides : kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside, kaempferol-3-*O*-diglucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-diglucoside-3'-*O*-xyloside.

Kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside has been isolated from *Athyrium filix-famina*² and from *Acystopteris japonica*³ and *Hypodematum crenatum* and *H. fauriei*⁴. Quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside has been reported from *Onoclea sensibilis*³. In

Table 1. UV-visible spectral and chromatographic data of flavonoid glycosides of *Athyrium solenopteris*

Sl. no.	Compd.	UV-visible spectra (nm)						R_f values		
		MeOH	NaOMe		AlCl ₃	AlCl ₃ /HCl	NaOAc	TBA : HOAc : H ₂ O (3 : 1 : 1)	HOAc (15%)	Sugar(s) present
			Immedia- tely	After 10 min						
1.	Kaempferol-3- <i>O</i> -glucoside	265, 363	283*, 432*	Decom.	265, 303 (sh) 356, 419	265 (sh), 303 (sh), 354, 419	273, 303 379	0.70	0.55	Glucose
2.	Kaempferol-3- <i>O</i> -diglucoside	264, 300 (sh), 346	275*, 318*, 401*	Decom.	272, 303, 356, 383	272, 301, 346, 380	272, 307, 388	0.62	0.66	Glucose
3.	Quercetin-3- <i>O</i> -glucoside	255, 262 (sh), 293, 356	271*, 323*, 404*	Decom.	358, 426	274, 358, 426	273, 320, 385	0.55	0.43	Glucose
4.	Quercetin-3- <i>O</i> -diglucoside	256, 264 (sh), 300 (sh), 356	272*, 315*, 412*	Decom.	273, 302 (sh), 365 (sh), 430	265, 300 (sh), 360, 394 (sh)	273, 320 (sh), 405	0.50	0.61	Glucose
5.	Quercetin-3- <i>O</i> -diglucoside-3'- <i>O</i> -xyloside	256, 266 (sh), 300 (sh), 357	273*, 310* (sh), 416*	Decom.	266, 300, 364, 392 (sh)	266, 300, 362, 390 (sh)	272, 322, 405	0.35	0.56	Glucose

*Increase in intensity.

the present investigation, presence of kaempferol and quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside in the advanced fern, *Athyrium solenopteris* may be due to the fact that complexity of flavonoids will increase with the morphogenetic advancement. Presence of glucose moiety in all the five flavonoid glycosides indicates that glucose is the primitive glycosylating sugar. As a result of photosynthesis and primary metabolism one would expect that glucose to be a primitive glycosylating moiety⁵. Flavonoid glucosides are commonly distributed in *Athyrioid* ferns. It is clear that several *Athyrioid* ferns possess kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside and quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside and hence these compounds may be considered as chemotaxonomic markers for the identification of *Athyrium solenopteris*.

Experimental

Air-dried fronds (250 g) of *A. solenopteris* was extracted with MeOH : H₂O (1 : 1 v/v; 1.5 lit.) under reflux for 6 h. The extract was subjected to low pressure column chromatography on Sephadex LH-20 (2.5 × 13 cm LH 20 column) using 20% methanol to 100% methanol to separate the extract into four bands. The flavonoid glycosides were found in bands 3 and 4. Two dimensional paper chromatographic work-up of each band was performed on Whatmann 3 filter paper⁶ using *t*-butanol : acetic acid : water (3 : 1 : 1) to

purify the flavonoids. UV-vis spectroscopy and shift reagents studies were performed following the method of Mabry *et al.*⁷. Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside was carried out with 5% ethanolic HCl and the aglycones were identified by comparison with authentic samples. Sugar moieties were identified by paper chromatography in comparison with authentic sugars and also by GLC as trimethylsilyl ether on 3% SE-52 on acid-washed Chromosorb W (column temperature 180°). For GLC Varian-3400 Series (FID) was used.

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